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D13.3 Implementation and Testing of Cultural Heritage Image Sharing Recommendations: DRI Case Study Report

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

CDIF	Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework
CODATA	Committee on Data of the International Science Council
CODATA-ICSTI	Committee on Data of the International Science Council - International Council for Scientific and Technical Information
DRI	Digital Repository of Ireland
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GLAM	Galleries, Libraries, Archives and Museums
IIIF	International Image Interoperability Framework
LOD	Linked Open Data
PID	Persistent Identifier
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RDF	Resource Description Framework

Executive summary

This is a summary report describing a use case for infrastructures that host image data for the cultural heritage sector. WorldFAIR Project Work Package 13 (Cultural Heritage) was tasked with providing a pathway to enabling wider adoption of image-sharing policies and practices in Galleries, Libraries, Archives and Museums ('GLAM' organisations) which align with the FAIR principles for research data¹, and are easily exchanged with commonly-used technologies and standards for sharing data in other domains of practice represented in the WorldFAIR Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF)².

This report builds on the findings of a mapping exercise in Deliverable 13.1, 'Cultural Heritage Mapping Report: Practices and policies supporting cultural heritage image sharing platforms'³ and outlines the process undertaken by the Digital Repository of Ireland (DRI) to respond to the general recommendations developed by an international working group in Deliverable 13.2, 'Cultural Heritage Image Sharing Recommendations Report'⁴, both through technical implementation and the development of best practice guidance for DRI members and the broader user community served by the repository.

Deliverable 13.3 describes the implementation plan and current state of activities, some of which will still be in progress at the time of publication. This is primarily a record of decisions made towards realising the five key recommendations. Further resources which document the outcomes of these activities will be made available in the DRI repository at the close of the WorldFAIR project. (The collection of DRI Publications⁵ is available to view.)

¹ <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

² <https://worldfair-project.eu/cross-domain-interoperability-framework>

³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.7659002>

⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7897244>

⁵ <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.3b591898r>

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1. Introduction

1.1 About DRI

The Digital Repository of Ireland (DRI) is a CoreTrustSeal-certified trustworthy digital repository for the preservation of Ireland’s humanities, cultural heritage, and social sciences data for long-term access. We provide stewardship of digital data from a range of member organisations including higher education institutions, cultural heritage institutions (the GLAM sector of galleries, libraries, archives, and museums), government agencies, county councils, and community archives. DRI is also an active research-performing organisation engaged in a rich range of research projects. DRI supports the principles of open research and makes data openly available in line with the FAIR data principles of findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability.

DRI operates on a membership model and provides stewardship of digital data from a variety of organisations and research projects. In line with its Equality, Diversity and Inclusion Policy⁶, DRI values a diversity of data and offers a limited number of deposit options and related benefits to organisations that operate on a non-funded basis as part of the DRI Community Archive Scheme⁷.

The Digital Repository of Ireland is leading the Cultural Heritage Case Study (WP13)⁸ for the WorldFAIR project.

1.2 The WorldFAIR project

The WorldFAIR project, managed by the Committee on Data of the International Science Council (CODATA)⁹, sets out to produce recommendations, interoperability frameworks and guidelines for FAIR data assessment. The WorldFAIR approach, outputs and modes of dissemination aim to significantly strengthen international cooperation in order to increase and mainstream FAIRness of data and digital objects. The project aims to join up disconnected and domain-specific initiatives on data management, data stewardship, and FAIR data practices, within and across disciplines and internationally, through eleven case studies.

As lead on the Cultural Heritage Case Study, DRI has already produced two reports. The first, D13.1

⁶ <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.pr76tx021>

⁷ <https://dri.ie/community-archive-scheme/>

⁸ <https://worldfair-project.eu/cultural-heritage/>

⁹ <https://codata.org/>

‘Cultural Heritage Mapping Report: Practices And Policies Supporting Cultural Heritage Image Sharing Platforms’¹⁰, provided an overview of practices guiding online digital image sharing by institutions charged with providing care and access to cultural memory, in order to identify how these practices might be adapted to promote and support the FAIR principles for data sharing. The report concluded with an examination of DRI’s position in this landscape as a significant resource for digital image data on Irish social and cultural heritage. The second report, D13.2 ‘Cultural Heritage Image Sharing Recommendations Report’¹¹, built on the understanding of what it means to support FAIR in the sharing of image data derived from GLAM collections. DRI looked at previous efforts by the sector towards FAIR alignment and established an expert Working Group on Cultural Heritage Image Sharing that would contribute to the development of recommendations broadly applicable to the work of the GLAMs, while also revealing opportunities for improving DRI’s commitment to enabling FAIR practice.

WorldFAIR Deliverable D13.1 demonstrated that DRI’s policies and practices were largely in line with common practice observed in the cultural heritage sector, and that the current repository design reflects similar technical and conceptual choices seen in a variety of popular image sharing platforms. The report recognised that significant efforts have been made by the GLAM sector towards supporting the interoperability of image collections, making it possible for the general public to discover much of the world’s cultural heritage through simple, user-friendly databases and web-based search engines. However, it was noted that the mechanisms by which these images are made available for research rely on historical access models aimed at the general user. D13.1 served as a starting point for discussion as to how GLAM professionals could better represent image collections for research and computational reuse.

Recommendations in D13.2 were envisioned as an extension of existing practices, which already enable the sector to present image collections for access by researchers and the general public, towards greater machine-actionability and interoperability with other types of data.

The Working Group on Cultural Heritage Image Sharing made five recommendations for the sharing of images in the cultural heritage sector (previously published in D13.2):

¹⁰ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7659002>

¹¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7897244>

Recommendation 1 Citation Model	A formal citation model for cultural heritage images should be adopted which recognises digital surrogates as research objects and includes references to revisions of either image data or metadata
Recommendation 2 Transparency	Information about the creation, management and preservation of files should be visible and understandable by both humans and machines
Recommendation 3 Data Documentation	The process of selection, scope and completeness of the data should always be documented
Recommendation 4 Licensing and Rights	Rights, licences and labels should be applied consistently and in a standardised way
Recommendation 5 Delivery	Improved support for identifier schemes, APIs and machine-readable contextual data

Table 1. Recommendations by the WorldFAIR Cultural Heritage Working Group in D13.2

At the heart of the recommendations is an understanding that the Collections as Data movement, which is building global community consensus through the Vancouver Statement on Collections as Data¹², work in the International GLAM Labs Community¹³ and the formation of a Research Data Alliance (RDA) Collections as Data Interest Group¹⁴, has laid significant groundwork in this area by leveraging decades of effort by GLAM organisations to advance best practices in information and data management.

1.3 Implementation phase overview

As shown in D13.1, the Digital Repository of Ireland’s policies, practices and technical infrastructure align with the technical and conceptual choices seen in a variety of popular image-sharing platforms for the cultural heritage sector. This places DRI in an excellent position to serve as a case study for alignment with the FAIR-enabling best practice recommendations that were made in D13.2 and aimed at the GLAM sector. A number of changes are currently under review or in development in the repository which affect both policy and workflows within DRI.

¹² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8342166>

¹³ <https://glamlabs.io/>

¹⁴ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/group/archives-and-records-professionals-research-data-ig/case-statement/collections-data-ig-charter>

DRI recognises that these changes impact internal resources, workflows and policies as well as member policies and resources, and require support from people in many different roles both within and external to the repository. As DRI is a repository not just for cultural heritage data provided by GLAM organisations, but also data deposited by researchers in the social sciences and humanities, any changes made to services to benefit GLAM members should not significantly alter the existing FAIR-enabling choices made for those communities. An example of this consideration can be seen in the choice to develop a cultural heritage citation style option that can be offered in addition to, and not in place of, DRI’s existing research data citation model.

As outlined below, none of the recommendations required significant modification of technical infrastructure, which can be attributed to DRI’s long history of support for the FAIR principles and prior adoption of FAIR-enabling technologies (see DRI’s statement on FAIR and Open Science¹⁵), but the work does present some conceptual challenges to established guidance and prevailing community practice. The areas in which DRI could best respond to many of the recommendations required significant effort to be put towards revisions of existing policies, workflows and training materials, as well as outreach to ensure community adoption. The implementation steps outlined below represent advancements in this work reflective of the overarching goal, as identified in D13.2, ‘to create approachable and sustainable methods to support cross-domain use of GLAM image collections as data, and to advocate for ongoing collaboration within the field’.

This report follows a simple structure. There are five sections, one for each recommendation in D13.2. Each section begins with a narrative introduction providing background discussion on the recommendation and describing the thought processes and considerations of the project team. This is then followed by information in a tabular form, restating the recommendation and FAIR alignment justifications from D13.2. The table continues, making reference to D13.1, outlining where DRI is positioned in relation to the recommendation and identifying opportunities for development or change, in order to offer better alignment with the FAIR principles. It then goes on to describe the proposed changes, and reports on the challenges and opportunities that arose as part of the implementation process. The table concludes with a summation of the result. Each section is presented in the same format, to facilitate readability and easy reference for other organisations considering similar approaches to the recommendations.

Heading	Definition
Recommendation	From D13.2 - A narrative overview of the recommendation
FAIR Alignment	From D13.2 - A narrative overview of how the recommendation is perceived to better align cultural heritage policy and practise with the FAIR principles

¹⁵ <https://dri.ie/fair-and-open-science/>

Snapshot	An overview of DRI's current position with regard to the recommendation, referencing D13.1
Analysis and actions	Analysis and suggestions for changes or improvements, concluding with recommended implementation choices and any current actions-in-progress
Timeline	Order of events in the implementation process
Discussion (process, outcomes, challenges, unexpected consequences)	Details of decisions made and how the implementation was approached within DRI's organisational structure encompassing: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Technical challenges and considerations arising during implementation planning - Unanticipated events and outputs, not considered during implementation planning
Results	Summary of recommendation delivery and outputs

Table 2. Structure of report.

2. Implementation of recommendations

2.1 Citation model

On developing the citation model for cultural heritage images, the project team was guided by both the structure and recommendations of CODATA's 2013 publication 'Out of cite, out of mind'¹⁶ and the Joint Declaration of Data Citation Principles¹⁷ developed by CODATA, the Research Data Alliance (RDA) and FORCE11. Consideration was given to the purpose of a citation, which serves multiple functions within a research domain: at its most basic level, a citation serves to direct the reader to a source. However, it also indicates where the responsibility lies in relation to both the creation and the publication of an object, as well as the source of the intellectual content of the metadata generated to describe that object. It allows for credit to be appropriately assigned, whether that be to the creator of a digital object or the stewarding institution responsible for original artefacts. In the GLAM sector it is recognised that many organisations are custodians and stewards of artefacts which exist in the public domain. However, the costs of creating intellectual content to describe and expose these artefacts (i.e. to enable findability) can be considerable, and mechanisms to enable credit for this effort are necessary.

¹⁶ https://www.jstage.jst.go.jp/article/dsj/12/0/12_OSOM13-043/_pdf

¹⁷ <https://doi.org/10.25490/a97f-egyk>

In the course of research undertaken for the development of the recommendations, issues were raised with existing guidance for citing digital cultural records. These records are often created from digitisation programmes designed to provide researchers with representative images or ‘digital surrogates’ of physical objects (e.g. APA Style Artwork References¹⁸, and the MLA Handbook ‘works cited’ style for artworks¹⁹). Existing citation styles focus on the content of images or the physical artefacts - rather than the digital files and their metadata - as the valuable research assets, creating a gap wherein the files used in data-driven research often cannot be precisely identified. This also deprioritises the intellectual contributions and potential rights of the stewards of those research collections as creators of the digital assets and metadata. This presents a potentially significant ethical barrier to the responsible reuse of cultural heritage collections, especially by those outside the humanities and social science research areas, in that reusers would in many cases incorrectly attribute the responsibility for contemporary information about historical objects to historical creators. Complicating matters further was the realisation that not very many cultural heritage collection platforms provide formatted citations to end users, possibly because of the complexity of fitting cultural heritage metadata properly into various bibliographic formats. In D13.1, it was noted that many organisations request a simple courtesy statement giving only the organisation’s name.

Issues around accurate citation and attribution are providing significant challenges across the wider research landscape at present where the combination of Big Data and Open Science has led to increased complexity around what is being cited, and how those citations can be best represented. The RDA Complex Citations Working Group²⁰ has recently been established (2023), with representatives from publishing houses and the research community, and is currently collecting use cases in advance of developing recommendations. Work is ongoing to address numerous challenges including: identification of multiple datasets across repositories; identification of smaller subsets of large datasets; citing dynamic datasets; citing different types of objects (software, data, samples), and providing citations for traceable results²¹. This group follows on from the work of the RDA Dynamic Citation Working Group which has already produced a set of 14 citation recommendations²².

In the GLAM sector, work funded by the EOSC Future project through an open call scheme provided the first steps towards a ‘FAIR-enabling Citation Model for Cultural Heritage Objects’²³. Of critical importance to the approach advocated by that project is an understanding that ‘the information resource and media type inform the vehicle of the represented cultural artefact’ which also underpins DRI’s recommendation in this area: the digital image is often the primary research object.

¹⁸ <https://apastyle.apa.org/style-grammar-guidelines/references/examples/artwork-references>

¹⁹ <https://style.mla.org/works-cited/works-cited-a-quick-guide/>

²⁰ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/complex-citations-working-group>

²¹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3r0RZ5E331Q>

²² <https://doi.org/10.1162/99608f92.be565013>

²³ <https://zenodo.org/communities/fair-cho/about>

DRI is presented as a case study in one of the project deliverables²⁴ and we consulted with this research project team in developing our citation recommendation. The key difference between the work of the ‘FAIR-enabling Citation Model for Cultural Heritage Objects’ project and that of WorldFAIR, is in the information we are attempting to surface. For WorldFAIR, the primary consideration is that the digital object is the ‘thing’ being referenced, an object worthy of study in its own right. For our colleagues in Padua, the focus is on demonstrating the relationships between the original artefacts and their representations.

In addition, and as noted in previous reports, the entire GLAM sector is witnessing a shift in its understanding of the information it stewards and is moving towards the Collections as Data paradigm^{25,26}. Many institutions have been exploring and publishing on this topic including the Library of Congress²⁷, the National Library of Scotland²⁸, KBR²⁹ and the German National Library (whose collections’ data has been available under a CCO licence since 2012)³⁰. Europeana has collaborated with CLARIN to use The Newspapers Collection as a (metadata) collection on their Virtual Language Observatory (VLO)³¹.

A final consideration of the project team is that we are living and working through a period of flux, when we are no longer thinking about our collections as surrogates for physical objects or artefacts, but as digital objects in their own right, worthy of study and analysis, citation and reference. A citation serves as both a starting point to allow the researcher entry to a knowledge system, and an exit point, summarising the key attributes of a resource. At the same time it should be concise enough to convey all of the necessary information, without replicating an entire metadata record.

Recommendation 1	Citation Model
Recommendation (D13.2)	
A formal citation model for cultural heritage images should be adopted which recognises digital surrogates as research objects and includes references to revisions of either image data or metadata.	
FAIR Alignment (D13.2)	

²⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8249060>

²⁵ <https://collectionsasdata.github.io/resources/>

²⁶ <https://zenodo.org/record/7789480>

²⁷ <https://labs.loc.gov/static/labs/work/reports/Experimental-Access-Digital-Collections-Data-Final-Report-v1.0.pdf>

²⁸ <https://data.nls.uk/>

²⁹ <https://www.kbr.be/en/projects/lod-isni/>

³⁰ <https://zenodo.org/record/7789480>

³¹ <https://pro.europeana.eu/post/clarin-and-europeana-make-discovery-and-processing-quick-and-easy-for-135-000-cultural-heritage-objects>

While no specific citation model is proposed by the FAIR principles, popular choices for disciplinary and generalist repositories follow citation models devised for publications. These focus on a limited number of metadata points: authorship, date, publisher and location. It is common for research data repositories to provide a version number and date as well, with each version sometimes also assigned a unique PID that links to a preserved record of current and prior versions. This is not necessarily possible for all cultural heritage images, as it presents a potentially substantial cost to collecting institutions to maintain multiple versions of data or metadata, while also risking perpetuating potentially problematic narratives by retaining metadata that should be recontextualised. The critical piece for alignment seems to be that the citation refers to a uniquely identifiable object, and alerts the researcher to the presence of changes made over time, not necessarily that all versions of the data remain available in perpetuity.

Snapshot - DRI in relation to Recommendation 1 - Citation Model

DRI's first Citation Policy was published in 2015³² and proposed a format which aligns with the recommendations published by the CODATA-ICSTI Task Group on Data Citation Standards and Practices³³. At the time the model was developed, it was recognised that the metadata supplied to the repository (whether academic research data or cultural heritage data) did not fit neatly into existing international standard bibliographic citation formats commonly required by journals in the social sciences and humanities disciplines. The DRI style aligned with common citation practice in prioritising the original creator of the intellectual content, date of publication, discovery location and relevant identifiers in the following format: Creator. (Date) Object title, Repository [Distributor], Depositor [Depositing Institution], DOI.

DRI follows best practice by offering a 'cite' button at collection, sub-collection and object level within the repository; Chicago, MLA and APA styles are also offered in addition to the bespoke DRI format.

DRI places the responsibility for creation and input of metadata on to its member (depositor) organisations. It provides oversight and clear guidance via documentation, tool tips, user guides and hands-on training, ultimately however, DRI devolves responsibility to the member organisations to ensure that published collections abide by recommended metadata standards and guidelines.

DRI's Current Citation Format in use for both research and cultural heritage resources

³² <https://repository.dri.ie/catalog/rx91h486p>; <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.rx91h486p-1>

³³ https://www.jstage.jst.go.jp/article/dsj/12/0/12_OSOM13-043/_pdf

{CREATOR}. (PUB_IN_DRI_Date) {TITLE}, {Digital Repository of Ireland} [Distributor], {DEPOSITING ORGANISATION} [Depositing Institution], {DOI URL}

Examples

Belleek. (2023) Belleek Candelabrum, Stags Head, Digital Repository of Ireland [Distributor], Hunt Museum, Limerick [Depositing Institution], <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.v4066406g>

Dagg, Jennifer, & Gray, Jane. (2021) RESCuE: Patterns of Resilience during Socioeconomic Crises among Households in Europe- Ireland, Digital Repository of Ireland [Distributor], Irish Qualitative Data Archive [Depositing Institution], <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.db797144j>

Analysis and actions

While DRI's citation style aligns with current best practice for the citation of research datasets, it was acknowledged that it presents challenges in terms of clearly communicating the responsibility for digital objects and metadata from the cultural heritage sector. It is expected in a standard bibliographic citation that the creator of a research dataset will also be the creator (or one of several creators) of both the metadata and the files deposited in a repository, and that the date of publication is also the date the data was made available. In reality, the creator of a cultural heritage object may be long deceased, with little say as to how their content is described or represented in digital environments.

It was also noted that the date element in use in the current citation was not necessarily reflective of the publication date metadata provided by the depositor, while the system-generated repository publication date was also not reflective of the date that material was acquired by the stewarding organisation or otherwise described and made publicly available, here referring to the many ways in which images may have been shared or used prior to deposit (i.e. published on social media, shared on a community group's webpage, exhibited in a digital showcase).

Taking into consideration that the life of a digital cultural heritage object may not start with deposit, a review of publication dates supplied by depositors revealed a wide range of uses of this field, from historical publication date of digitised texts or performances of works, not associated with the digital file. At this time, it was decided to leave the Dublin Core metadata element for publication out of the citation reference but include the system-generated publication date on the collection and object landing pages.

As noted in D13.1 'The mutability of cultural heritage records is not only an important factor for accessibility but also integral to the institution's ability to maintain relevance and respect for the communities they serve'. GLAMS rarely expose these changes to the end-user, although there

may be various internal methods of recording this information. In order to support the identification of versions a temporal element has been added to the citation to indicate when the record or object was viewed/retrieved by the user.

The following was proposed:

DRI would continue to support its current general research data citation style while also adding a cultural heritage specific style that appropriately reflected the responsibility of the stewarding organisation in creating the metadata and files made available for research reuse.

Key considerations for the development of the cultural heritage style included:

Use of 'Creator' is preferred over 'Author' to more closely align with Dublin Core terminology and common usage in the sector.

Addition of elements

The descriptive metadata provided by the depositor can add significant value to the citation and, where the values are populated, it is proposed that the following are used:

- Creation Date*
- Type

Addition of element labels

In order to disambiguate similar elements, and add clarity to human interpretation, labels should be provided as part of the citation. This is not required for all elements. Labels should be indicated by use of square brackets e.g. [Type].

Access Timestamp

A time should be presented to indicate when the resource was accessed by the end user. While this information does not conclusively indicate version, combined with other data it may be useful for identifying the version accessed. This timestamp will be preceded by the label 'Accessed: '.

In the process of developing the cultural heritage style, it was determined that the existing citation style for research data would benefit from minor revisions as well:

Renaming of 'Distributor' to 'Publisher'

The term 'Distributor' should be renamed to 'Publisher' to accurately reflect DRI's role in the process as the digital publisher of the collection/object.

Renaming of 'Depositing Organisation' to 'Depositor' to allow for individual or research project deposits in addition to member organisations.

Addition of elements

- Type

Addition of element labels

- [Type]
- [Publisher]
- [Depositor]

Timestamp

A time should be automatically generated to indicate when the resource was accessed by the end user. While this information does not conclusively indicate version, combined with other data it may be useful for identifying the version accessed. This timestamp will be preceded by the term ‘Accessed: ’.

In both citation styles, a suggested revision to the order of elements was proposed with the following considerations to aid human interpretation:

Syntax

- The nesting of dates alongside the elements that they are most closely linked to helps to disambiguate date values.
- The positioning of Depositor at the beginning of the cultural heritage citation to indicate the entity responsible for the digital object, and disambiguate from ‘Creator’ or ‘Author’.
- Minor formatting to aid readability, such as ‘Title’ being italicised.

Timeline

November 2023	December 2023	January 2024	February 2024	March 2024	April 2024	May 2024
Review DRI’s citation model			Testing and implementation		Training	

Discussion (process, outcomes, challenges, unexpected consequences)

The process of review was initially desk-based but evolved into a collaborative process leveraging the expertise of colleagues working on similar projects in the Collections as Data community. Feedback from the FAIR-enabling citation model for Cultural Heritage Objects group during their review of citation practices in cultural heritage repositories such as DRI, the Archaeology Data

Service³⁴, and PHAIDRA³⁵, gave a level of confidence in the requirements for a format revision³⁶. The cultural heritage model proposed by that group was not adopted as-is at DRI due to timing and a difference of approach, as discussed above.

DRI does recommend a one-to-one approach for cataloguing, which encourages users to think of the digital assets as the materials being described, but the repository also acknowledges the usefulness of content-specific metadata being valuable to researchers accessing digital representations of historical records. It was deemed to be outside of the scope of work for WorldFAIR to make changes to this practice.

Technical resources were required to assist with implementation and while the task itself was fairly straightforward, there was some complexity in developing the code and ensuring the citation options consistently produced the correct values. Additional depositor training will be required to refresh and reinforce member's understanding of metadata elements.

There were questions raised early on about the importance of retaining descriptive metadata in the citation if it did not directly relate to the usability and discoverability of the data (i.e. retaining the name of the original creator and date of creation of the content represented by the files and described by the metadata). After all, a citation style is not designed to replicate the metadata record, merely to point to it. However, it was also felt that the citation should acknowledge best practice and guidance from the cultural heritage sector in citing memory collections, which often includes the name of the creator of the content and historical dates of creation (e.g. University of Leeds Harvard: Museum Artefact³⁷).

Challenges

***Creation Date vs. Subjects (Temporal)**

In DCMI Metadata Terms, the Creation Date may refer to the date of creation of either the digital or original (physical) resource. DRI depositors have largely used this field to provide dates associated with the content of a digital asset (e.g. a physical artefact) rather than the date of creation of digital files, although the usage is not consistent and may cause some confusion. A review was undertaken to determine the number of past deposits this may affect if Creation Date is used in the citation to refer to the content. It was determined that the field is almost exclusively used by depositors to refer to a historical date associated with the content. Subjects (Temporal) was proposed as a preferred field option for disambiguation, as this should also refer to dates associated with the content of the resource, although not exclusively creation dates (for instance,

³⁴ <https://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/>

³⁵ <https://phaidra.cab.unipd.it/>

³⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8249060>

³⁷ <https://library.leeds.ac.uk/referencing-examples/9/leeds-harvard/521/museum-artefact>

it may indicate a period of time in which the object was in use). In addition, the Dublin Core element Coverage, of which (Temporal) is a sub-property, is not available in bulk ingests from other DRI-supported metadata standards such as EAD, MODS or MARC. After analysis of the values currently provided to the repository it appears that Creation Date is the most accurate representation of depositor-provided metadata for originating dates referring to historical content. Others seeking to implement DRI's citation format for cultural heritage objects may prefer another option, depending on local usage and guidance, to populate this value from.

***Published Date vs. Publication Date**

DRI inserts a system-generated date into the citation that reflects the date and time that the citation was published in the repository. This date does not appear in the metadata record, which is a source of confusion for end users who see a 'publication date' metadata element in the entry that does not precisely match the date provided in the citation. It was determined that it would be beneficial to retain DRI's published date as part of the citation, but to also add this piece of information visibly to the metadata record.

Result

At the time of publication, DRI is reviewing and testing the additional recommended citation format as well as revisions to the existing general format which the depositor may select depending on the type of material being cited:

DRI General Citation Format

Creator. *Title*. Type [Type] Digital Repository of Ireland (Pub_in_DRI_Date) [Publisher] Depositor [Depositor] DOI URL (Accessed:DATEtimestamp)

Examples

Conlon,C, McDonnell, T, Barrett, M, Cummins, F, Deasy, C, Hensey, C, McAuliffe, E, & Nicholson, E. *Interview with Emergency Medicine Clinician 9*. Text [Type] Digital Repository of Ireland (2022) [Publisher] Irish Qualitative Data Archive [Depositor] <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.bc38m699h> (Accessed: 2024/03/20)

Dagg, Jennifer, & Gray, Jane. *RESCuE, Photograph contributed by 'Sam,' HU006*. Image [Type] Digital Repository of Ireland (2021) [Publisher] Irish Qualitative Data Archive [Depositor] <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.8336wq348> (Accessed: 2024/03/20)

Fig 1 - Revised DRI General Citation Format (detailed breakdown)

DRI Cultural Heritage Citation Format

Depositor [Depositor] *Title*. Creator (Creation_Date). Type [Type] Digital Repository of Ireland (Pub_In_DRI_Date) [Publisher] DOI URL (Accessed:·DATimestamp)

Examples

An Post Museum and Archive [Depositor] *50th Anniversary of Na Píobairí Uileann*. An Post (2018). Image [Type] Digital Repository of Ireland (2021) [Publisher] <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.zs26b015x> (Accessed: 2024/03/20)

Hunt Museum, Limerick [Depositor] *Belleek Candelabrum, Stags Head*. Belleek (19th Century) 3D [Type] Digital Repository of Ireland (2023) [Publisher] <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.v4066406g> (Accessed: 2024/03/20)

Fig 2 - DRI Cultural Heritage Citation Format (detailed breakdown)

2.2 Transparency

This recommendation was developed in recognition of the importance of sharing technical information about the origins and management of digital files as objects of research. In the cultural heritage sector, digital image files have become invaluable tools for communicating visual information about a diverse range of materials, including original physical or born-digital objects, historical and contemporary events, artistic practices, archival records, computational renderings, etc. Despite their critical function in digital research, however, digital files often operate as a kind of invisible delivery media, or mere windows onto the ‘real life’ objects they depict³⁸. Metadata may be provided which describes the content of a file rather than the file itself, or which mixes the content and file information together, making it harder to computationally distinguish file metadata from content metadata for reuse at scale.

Fortunately, much technical information is available both about how files are created and how they are maintained by many repositories stewarding the data over time. Embedded technical metadata, which is captured by the digital device at the point of creation, is stored in a machine-readable format that is easily used by operating systems and programs to sort, organise and aid discoverability without ever presenting the raw information directly to the end user. This information is also captured and read by many digital preservation workflows, making it readily available in preservation environments.

In D13.1, standards and practices related to embedded metadata were reviewed as a potential means of delivering information about the technical history and responsibility for image files as research objects (see D13.1, section 2.2.5, ‘Embedded metadata’). It was found that while standards for structuring and exchanging embedded metadata do exist, there was little agreed-upon community practice for checking, editing or augmenting this information: “Embedded metadata seems to have uneven uptake across the cultural heritage sector, with little advice on the topic appearing in digitisation policy and guidance documents. As part of their ingest process each content provider decides the workflow and technology that is best suited to their needs and therefore controls the types, and richness, of the metadata embedded”³⁹.

A Working Group of the Smithsonian Institution produced a set of *Basic Guidelines for Minimal Descriptive Embedded Metadata in Digital Images* in 2010, which summarised a consensus reached across the institution for a minimum proposed set of embedded descriptive metadata: required fields included title, copyright notice, source and creator; while suggested fields were date, description, keywords, credit/provider, job identifier and headline (or caption)⁴⁰. The Embedded

³⁸ D13.2, p. 18

³⁹ D13.1, p. 30

⁴⁰ <https://repository.si.edu/handle/10088/9719>

Metadata Subcommittee of the Cataloging and Metadata Standards Committee at the Visual Resources Association developed a set of tools and produced a series of training videos to support their implementation, but there does not appear to be a formal recommendation associated with these resources⁴¹. There are few other examples of best practice documentation for embedded metadata in the cultural heritage sector (although this may be because technical standards from organisations like IPTC do already provide general guidance⁴²), which seems to stem from concerns that providing full metadata within the image file risks either disseminating flawed descriptions or producing metadata records that will fall out of sync with their files when those records inevitably change⁴³.

It is unclear whether many cultural heritage institutions are monitoring the persistence of embedded metadata across versions and formats, or taking proactive steps to embed additional descriptive metadata into the files to aid interpretation and reuse. It is also unclear to what extent this descriptive metadata, which may be added during the file creation or digitisation process by different persons than those responsible for the creation of descriptive records, may therefore differ from information presented in a metadata record. A study of cultural heritage images on the web in 2018 found that ‘a remarkably low percentage of the images analysed contain metadata, that no links exist between image embedded metadata and its metadata record or the pages of the websites analysed...’⁴⁴. For DRI to responsibly share technical metadata available from image files, a review of how the workflows of members could support this recommendation was needed.

⁴¹ <https://www.vraweb.org/embedded-metadata-tools>

⁴² <https://iptc.org/standards/photo-metadata/guidelines-support>

⁴³ <https://online.vraweb.org/index.php/vrab/article/view/123>

⁴⁴ <https://doi.org/10.1108/LHT-03-2017-0053>

Recommendation 2	Transparency
Details of Recommendation - as per 13.2	
Information about the creation, management and preservation of files should be visible and understandable by both humans and machines.	
FAIR Alignment - as per 13.2	
<p>In the sciences, instrument data is augmented by information about the instrument, which is no different than providing the user with digital capture information in digitised or born-digital collections material. A particular lens in a particular camera may impart defects or represent the source material differently from another camera, which could influence both human and mechanical interpretation. As data provenance is also key for interoperability and reuse, the provenance of file types generated by the institution in the course of preservation work should be prioritised to support ongoing computational use. This may come in the form of technical metadata that is readily available and embedded in image files, or it may be satisfied by collection-level metadata that describes the digitisation and/or digital preservation process. The level of preservation provided by the institution will influence the amount and type of metadata made available⁴⁵.</p>	
Snapshot - DRI in relation to Recommendation 2 - Transparency	
<p>DRI captures information about files that are uploaded to the repository as part of the deposit process, but the digitisation workflows that produce the metadata are the responsibility of the member organisations contributing to the repository. If embedded metadata is available in the files, this is retained and stored in the preservation copy of the file but may be stripped out in access copies generated by the repository workflow.</p> <p>As summarised in D13.1, DRI also produces and retains metadata about technical preservation actions carried out on image files, but does not make this information publicly available. DRI allows depositors to edit and update metadata records associated with their collections and does not maintain a public record of version changes, although version information (such as date, time and user account accessing and editing either data or metadata) are recorded internally and made visible to the depositor only for management purposes.</p>	

⁴⁵ <https://ndsa.org/publications/levels-of-digital-preservation/>

Analysis and recommended actions

In exploring whether technical metadata captured and retained by the repository workflows could or should be shared more readily with end users, several issues were identified by both DRI staff and the WorldFAIR Cultural Heritage Image Sharing Working Group:

1. As this information is often captured in behind-the-scenes processes and is not always accessible in user-friendly displays, concerns were raised about whether depositors were aware that they may be sharing potentially sensitive information through image files. Embedded metadata may contain information regarding the date and location that an original photograph was taken, revealing for example, the precise time and date in which someone participated in an event, the exact location of an archaeological find of sensitive cultural origins, or the home of a person voluntarily scanning personal records for donation to an archive. These pieces of information are automatically captured and may be retained even through versioning and editing workflows. DRI had previously decided to strip embedded metadata out of system-generated access files when these concerns were present.
2. Some cultural heritage institutions embed descriptive metadata to help identify and control the reuse of records that are made openly available, but are not necessarily openly licensed for reuse. (In practice, images are often accessible for viewing, without necessarily granting the viewer permission to reuse the image.) The process of adding or editing descriptive metadata as part of a digitisation workflow could potentially be destructive to existing machine-generated metadata, and revealing that edited metadata to the end user may inadvertently imply that what the end user is seeing is authentic, *original* metadata.

In considering how DRI could best utilise embedded image file metadata to provide greater visibility of technical information about the format of digital assets, it was agreed that DRI first needed to examine the workflows of members contributing image files to the repository. Using that information then could provide feedback on workflows around embedded metadata that could contribute to an overall best practice recommendation. A survey was proposed to capture more information about user workflows to target areas where practices could also improve descriptive as well as technical metadata.

DRI issued a survey to its membership, **Member Digitisation Workflows for 2D Images**, which ran from 7 December 2023 – 31 January 2024 (see [Appendix I](#)). There were 20 respondents to the survey, giving us a response rate of about 35%. Representation from professional fields of work across the cultural heritage sector was captured (note that some institutions gave multiple responses): 17 Archives, 12 Libraries, 5 Museums and 11 Higher Education Institutions.

Survey results

We learned from the survey that about half of the members who responded are adding descriptive metadata to their files, which may include rights, licences, keywords, PIDs, etc. Most affirmed that the technical metadata generated by their digitisation workflow was retained by all versions of the files (Fig 3). Only one respondent indicated that embedded metadata was not retained across all versions of files generated by their workflow.

Fig 3. Results from the survey question 'Do you add or remove metadata from the image file?'

It seems likely that DRI members will have both technical and descriptive metadata that may be of value to reveal to end users. Many, though not all, are aware of the information captured in the files themselves and would prioritise the retention of the following key fields in any future-focused preservation actions on DRI's part (Fig 4).

What metadata is critical to preserve?

Fig 4. Results from the survey question ‘What metadata is critical to preserve?’

Implementation timeline

November 23	December 23	January 24	February 24	March 24	April 24	May 24
Survey prep	Survey of DRI membership		Review of survey results		Member Training	

Discussion (process, outcomes, challenges, unexpected consequences)

In exploring how best to use the information gathered, it was determined that some of this information overlapped with the information requested by the datasheets that DRI was also investigating as part of the work described in section [2.3 Data Documentation](#), below, and that producing a narrative report for depositors showing embedded metadata found in files uploaded to the repository could give the depositor better control over what was shared while also encouraging them to engage with the datasheet.

One technical consideration arose from the repository’s workflow, which requires a depositor to fill out the metadata record first and then add the digital asset. It is not possible to auto-populate metadata records in advance with information from embedded metadata in files. If a depositor

has saved their work and considers the metadata record complete, automatically inserting new information could potentially lead them to unknowingly publishing records with conflicting metadata.

A helpful outcome of this work, in addition to encouraging depositors to utilise and share embedded metadata and information about digitisation workflows, is that depositors may be better able to check for occasional deviations between the rights or licences supplied in the file metadata versus in the metadata record.

Result

DRI is in the process of developing guidance for members managing embedded metadata in files in response to the survey findings, in order to encourage consistency of practice across the DRI's membership. The results from the survey are available in Zenodo as Digital Repository of Ireland Member Digitisation Workflows for 2D Image Files: Survey Questions and Dataset⁴⁶.

Next steps towards the end of the project will likely include some overlap with work towards a datasheet recommendation (see next section). This could include providing depositors with an ingest report that would suggest possible improvements to the metadata record, based on information available in a file's embedded metadata, calling attention to any issues with implied rights or licences within the file itself.

2.3 Data documentation

The recommendation for documentation is based on the observation in D13.1 that specific acquisition and digitisation decisions are rarely communicated to the end user, which can obscure the provenance, scope, purpose, gaps or biases in the way that cultural heritage collections are acquired and shared. Even in cases where this additional information is provided to the end user, it may not be easily accessible for computational reuse.

Datasheets, originally proposed by the machine learning community as a mechanism for documenting datasets used for training and evaluating machine learning models, are machine-readable documents formatted to uniformly present contextual information⁴⁷. Although developed in a different disciplinary context and reuse scenario, the introduction of datasheets for machine learning surfaced an awareness among GLAM professionals that future reusers may not have access to the institutional knowledge that can and should inform the responsible reuse of

⁴⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10849045>

⁴⁷ <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1803.09010>

cultural data. Datasheets addressed an alarming limitation in how poorly machines could perceive absence, context, audience and the general complexity of records. The original datasheets were designed to support responsible reuse, encouraging dataset creators to provide information about known biases in the dataset that could contribute to problematic conclusions derived from such critical techniques as distant viewing, recognising that there are currently no measures to mitigate against racism, misogyny, discrimination, exclusion or toxicity in historical data: “A growing body of work shows that many problems in fairness, accountability, transparency, and ethics in machine learning systems are rooted in decisions surrounding the data collection and annotation process”⁴⁸.

In the past 12 to 18 months, much work has been done to adapt datasheets for different purposes in the cultural heritage sector, perhaps most notably in the management of web archives⁴⁹. DRI staff were fortunate to be able to attend training hosted by the Digital Preservation Coalition and the British Library on ‘Datasheets for Datasets: Describing Web Archives’ during the project⁵⁰.

The Library of Congress is trialling a ‘Digitized Books Data Package’ which includes 6 components: the dataset itself, metadata (in CSV, JSON, and text), technical README, a sample dataset, a data processing plan, and a data cover sheet⁵¹. In late 2023, a Europeana Working Group produced a recommendation and proposed template for Datasheets for Digital Cultural Heritage⁵², which is currently being tested in several cultural heritage institutions across Europe. The DRI project team intends to take the learnings from these projects to adapt – not reimagine – a datasheet for DRI.

Recommendation 3	Data Documentation
Details of Recommendation - as per 13.2	
The process of selection, scope and completeness of the data should always be documented.	
FAIR alignment - as per 13.2	
In research projects, the scope of the research question is often included as part of the documentation so that users understand not only what is available within the dataset, but the selection process that produced that data, whether curated from a larger dataset or compiled from multiple sources. GLAM organisations rarely ‘package’ collections in ways that completely document the history of the object in the organisation, instead providing links that indicate relationships to other collections materials, policies guiding decision-making, or statements about acquisition and selection at the aggregate level. Here the production of data documentation	

⁴⁸ <https://doi.org/10.1145/3351095.3372829>

⁴⁹ <https://www.jisc.ac.uk/events/ai-ready-library-collections-the-practicalities>

⁵⁰ <https://www.dpconline.org/news/news-datasheets-for-datasets-workshop>

⁵¹ <https://data.labs.loc.gov/digitized-books/?loclr=blogsig>

⁵² <https://zenodo.org/records/8375034>

designed to provide a parallel to a research dataset's README file is recommended, but any documents provided which share institutional perspectives should be acknowledged as fulfilling this need.

Snapshot - DRI in relation to Recommendation 3 - Data Documentation

DRI makes a clear connection between datasets in the repository and the responsible institutions or depositors, through the use of organisational logos on metadata records and a top-level navigation menu that allows users to Browse by Organisation⁵³, but relationships between those institutions and their communities, donors, contexts for acquisition and selection for digital delivery, etc., may be more difficult to ascertain from the metadata provided.

A depositor guide, 'How to DRI: Contextual Information'⁵⁴, outlines the process for providing additional documentation and provides further guidance in this regard. Functionality at the point of ingest, via a webform, allows the depositor to associate documentation with specific collections. The process of selecting 'Add Documentation' creates the 'has Documentation' and the 'Is Documentation For' relationship between the collection and the object. Supporting documentation is issued with its own unique DOI.

Within the metadata records themselves, DRI strongly advocates for the inclusion of contextual data from depositors, particularly for research outputs. As noted in D13.1 'Cultural Heritage Mapping Report', "the collection record largely facilitates transparency around the context for objects entering the repository. In that respect, the DRI's conceptual model uses the collection record effectively as a provenance record, analogous to a dataset's README file or supporting documentation. Provenance information is also minimally available within the object record, usually in the fields allocated to Rights and Depositing Organisation"⁵⁵.

DRI supports the ingest of several established metadata standards, including Dublin Core, Qualified Dublin Core, EAD, MODS or MARC XML formats and this metadata is made available to download as XML. Contributors are encouraged to use community-recognised vocabularies to select standard data values when ingesting. DRI also has a Collections Development Policy that provides an overview of the collecting areas and types of data considered appropriate for the repository⁵⁶.

⁵³ <https://repository.dri.ie/organisations>

⁵⁴ <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.sn00qc64j>

⁵⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7659002>

⁵⁶ <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.kk91v774c-2>

DRI supports either partial or full removal of metadata and data from the repository in its Withdraw Data Policy⁵⁷.

Analysis and recommended actions

The objective of implementing this recommendation is to create and disseminate information about DRI collections as data in a structured manner, whenever possible, and in a narrative form, whenever necessary. The request for contextual data should not be so intensive that it creates a hardship for depositors (particularly those availing of the low-to-no funding Community Archive Scheme) to provide the information to a high standard, and it should be flexible so that there is low threshold for compliance (similar to a Dublin Core record). Recognising that recontextualisation of historical data is laborious and intensive for the research process, DRI takes the position that any data added is good data added.

A datasheet may be used for technical as well as administrative and descriptive metadata, highlighting the potential differences between a physical collection and a derived digital dataset, as well as the digitisation pipeline that produced the digital assets that are being interrogated as research objects. They are also documents that can be updated over time, presenting institutions with a public-facing resource that can document the social impact of the dataset and changes to its metadata while also documenting reuse cases and examples.

DRI currently has a recommended supplementary information sheet that researchers in the social sciences or humanities can use to add descriptive context to their deposited collections. It could be adapted for use by cultural heritage organisations as well; however, since there is currently a datasheet model being tested by a community of peers, Datasheets for Digital Cultural Heritage Datasets⁵⁸, DRI project staff recommend the adoption of the existing template as-is to provide feedback to the template developers. It is worth noting that developers of the cultural heritage datasheet intend to modify the template based on feedback from stakeholders such as DRI, which may result in changes to the format, functionality and structure.

⁵⁷ <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.Or96mp375>

⁵⁸ <https://zenodo.org/records/8375034>

Timeline					
December 23	Jan 2024	Feb 2024	Mar 2024	Apr 2024	May 2024
Review and research			Testing		
Discussion (Process, outcomes, challenges, unexpected consequences)					
<p>Since the publication of this recommendation in D13.2, and as noted above, work in this area by a Europeana Working Group, the Library of Congress and the British Library has focused attention on datasheets as a preferred contextual documentation method for cultural heritage collections.</p> <p>Rather than having to create its own bespoke datasheet, the DRI project team is in the fortunate position of being able to adapt the work of others and has selected the ‘Datasheets for Digital Cultural Heritage Datasets’ model for testing. The Europeana Working Group is currently developing a user-friendly, fillable version of the template that would integrate guidance and allow for different format outputs (markdown, PDF, etc.). While this is an advantage technically for DRI, it does mean that DRI’s timeline for testing will be dependent on the timely release of the template tool.</p> <p>The task of appending datasheets to objects and collections does not appear, at this stage, to have any major technical implications.</p>					
Result					
<p>DRI will utilise existing functionality in the repository which supports the addition of contextual documents to collection descriptions to trial the Datasheet for Digital Cultural Heritage Datasets with contributing members, providing feedback to the Europeana Working Group on further development of the template.</p>					

2.4 Licensing and rights

DRI is a member-based organisation which provides preservation and access to the digital collections of its depositors via the repository. As it stands, DRI only accepts content in which the depositor holds, or is authorised to hold, copyright. DRI acts as the publisher and steward of this digital content. Depositors manage the ingest of all data and associated metadata, including appropriate copyright and licence statements.

DRI provides oversight and clear guidance via documentation, form tips and user guides, and it also provides hands-on training. However, the member is responsible for the choice and application of terms. While DRI encourages the use of machine actionable licence statements from Creative Commons⁵⁹ and Open Data Commons⁶⁰, we recognise that many members, for historical reasons, prefer free-text statements or a combination of rights and licences that may be less straightforwardly interpreted by machines. The objective of implementing this recommendation is to make explicit rights and licensing statements in both human-readable and machine-actionable forms.

As flagged in D13.1, there are challenges in applying licences that extend beyond issues such as consistent formatting and interpretability of statements (see D13.1, section 2.1.4, ‘Rights and licences’). There are often problems of distinction between a cultural heritage object, its digital twin, and access versions of the same, which can lead to confusion in applying licences (and making statements about rights). In the EU, digital cultural heritage objects are subject to the European Copyright Directive⁶¹ and may be in the public domain (per Article 14, ‘Works of visual art in the public domain’) or ‘out of commerce’ (per Article 8, ‘Use of out-of-commerce works and other subject matter by cultural heritage institutions’), but stewarded by an institution which then generates new files and provides administrative, descriptive and technical metadata to facilitate access to the object’s content, and therefore chooses to apply licences to the digital representation⁶². These licences may or may not be supported by a given legal jurisdiction, making it challenging for cultural heritage institutions to use common practice to determine what combinations of rights and licences they are legally able to apply. A recent study, ‘The Accuracy of Rights Statements on Europeana.eu’⁶³, determined that “22% of 182 digital objects had an incorrect rights statement”, in which a public domain work was either listed as ‘In Copyright’ or issued a CC licence, although further investigation utilising a larger dataset revealed that many of the CC licences were CC0, which clearly waived any possible rights acquired after digitisation. Although the situation may not be as problematic as the study implies, it does highlight the complexity of the work now facing collections professionals who are required not only to communicate the rights status of an object but grant appropriate blanket permissions for reuse.

Anecdotally, objects are occasionally licenced incorrectly by depositors at DRI. In the example below, the depositor had entered their rights information via a free text field, selecting a phrase that did not clearly communicate their intention, which was to waive any rights in the object. The licence field also displayed incorrect information because the drop-down defaults to ‘All Rights Reserved’.

⁵⁹ <https://creativecommons.org>

⁶⁰ <https://opendatacommons.org/licenses/>

⁶¹ DIRECTIVE (EU) 2019/790, <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2019/790/oj>

⁶² <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40319-020-00961-8>

⁶³ <https://www.kl.nl/wp-content/uploads/2018/02/The-Accuracy-of-Rights-Statements.pdf>

<p>Rights No rights statement</p> <p>Licence All Rights Reserved. This object is not licenced for general reuse. Please see Rights Statement for more detail.</p>

Fig 5. Display from an object record page showing a mismatch between declared rights and applied licences, which has since been corrected by the depositor.

Further complicating this work is that licences and rights may also be applied to the *metadata* attached to the digital asset/object as well the digital asset/object itself, which is not common practice for digital cultural heritage. Europeana offers some guidance on attribution where these rights may differ⁶⁴, but also requires that metadata be supplied with a CC0 licence to the Europeana platform. Transposed into Irish law in 2021, the European Open Data Directive asserts that data provided by public bodies be “open by default and design”⁶⁵.

Recommendation 4	Licensing & Rights
Details of Recommendation - as per 13.2	
Rights, licences and labels should be applied consistently and in a standardised way.	
FAIR alignment - as per 13.2	
Explicit rights and licensing statements are a requirement for all aspects of the FAIR data workflow, from discovery to reuse, and this information should be available in both human-readable and machine-actionable forms. The application of standardised rights statements for digital files is probably far more feasible within the sector than machine-actionable licences, however, and should be acknowledged as good practice. Despite the complexity of this work, recognising other forms of attribution, ownership and care should also be prioritised.	
Snapshot - DRI in relation to Recommendation 4 - Licensing and Rights	
Since DRI manages digital objects, we encourage members to apply rights and licences which most appropriately represent the reuse permissions that would apply to the digital asset and its accompanying metadata. At the moment however, the rights and licence fields displayed in the metadata record only describe permissions associated with the digital asset. As noted in D13.1, depositors are made aware of DRI’s metadata licence requirements via provisions in the Depositor Terms and Conditions, which reserve the right for the repository to make available	

⁶⁴ <https://www.europeana.eu/en/rights/usage-guidelines-for-metadata>

⁶⁵ <https://data.gov.ie/pages/open-data-directive>

certain metadata fields [Title, Creator, Publisher, Publication Year and DOI] under a public domain dedication⁶⁶. Depositor and Organisational Manager agreements also inform the depositor that they must hold rights in/over a resource in order to apply a licence to it in the repository.

Rights and licences are applied by the depositor at point of ingest, using the web-based ingest form. To a large extent, depositors have used the Dublin Core rights element to provide a free text narrative to explain any rights held in and over a resource. Licences are only available via a drop-down menu. When a user downloads an asset, rights and licence information is bundled with it in a .txt file called Licence.

The metadata record and the downloadable licence file do not clearly communicate to end users the potential differences in the licence for the metadata versus the digital asset. The End User Agreement⁶⁷ indicates that users must “abide by the appropriate copyright and licence statements applied to digital object and metadata”, but there is no blanket metadata licence statement provided, or again, a licence for the metadata within the metadata record. The Licensing Statement⁶⁸ that appears in the footer of the repository website actually refers only to content provided by DRI and on the DRI website as a whole.

DRI offers a number of publications in which the repository’s position on metadata supplied to the repository is made clearer, and which can provide guidance to both depositors and end users. Current policy and guidance in this area is covered primarily by DRI publications ‘Copyright, Licensing and Open Access’⁶⁹, ‘Qualified Dublin Core and the Digital Repository of Ireland’⁷⁰ and ‘Metadata and the DRI’⁷¹. References in these documents indicate that all metadata is either CC0 or CC-BY.

Analysis and recommended actions

There is ambiguity about DRI’s licensing of metadata in its current documentation, which requires clarification and updating to ensure consistency. DRI also needs to ensure that any changes to licences adhere to legal obligations in existing agreements with depositors. It is possible to change terms going forward; however, existing agreements will need to be considered for past deposits. A review of documentation will clarify and identify if there is a need for engagement

⁶⁶ <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.1544r4085>

⁶⁷ <https://repository.dri.ie/pages/terms>

⁶⁸ <https://dri.ie/licensing-statement/>

⁶⁹ <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.v4066146t>

⁷⁰ <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.5425zz83q>

⁷¹ <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.bz60sj10d>

with past depositors on this issue, and whether any changes can be applied immediately to retrospective collections or should just be introduced for future collections.

The following was proposed:

It was determined that DRI could provide more easily accessible and interpretable information about rights and licences to both depositors and end users by providing depositors with options to apply standardised, community-approved rights statements in addition to providing a metadata licence statement clearly within the metadata record.

Apply a CC0 licence⁷² for metadata as the default standard

An explicit licence statement pertaining to the metadata in the repository is not available to end users. DRI will provide a statement that clearly indicates the CC0 licence applies to the metadata, or in exceptional circumstances ([see Appendix II](#)), a CC-BY licence requiring attribution. In addition to technical implementation, this change requires updating of a range of documents, guidance and tool tips.

Require the application of Rights Statements⁷³ for objects

It is proposed that DRI implements a machine-readable standard vocabulary for rights, with the facility to provide additional rights information in a free-text field retained.

Timeline

November 23	December 23	January 24	February 24	March 24	April 24	May 24
Review DRI Documentation			Agree Licences		Training	
			Tech Implementation			

Discussion (process, outcomes, challenges, unexpected consequences)

The process of review was initially desk-based. Implementation discussions took place within internal taskforces, with a final approval by the DRI Management Team, the body tasked with making significant changes to repository functionality, on the delivery of a CC0 licence statement for metadata records. The development of a formal derogation process to allow depositors to request CC-BY under specific circumstances was also approved.

Support for this recommendation also relies on changes to the citation format proposed in Recommendation 1, which should correctly point the user to the depositor as the rights holder and entity requesting attribution when the CC-BY licence is used.

⁷² <https://creativecommons.org/public-domain/cc0/>

⁷³ <https://rightsstatements.org/>

All CC licence options were already available to DRI depositors in a drop-down menu in the ingest workflow. There was concern that the addition of all twelve Rights Statements would be confusing, especially populating those that were unlikely to be of significant use to DRI depositors (i.e. No Copyright - In the United States). It was decided to deploy a selection of four Rights Statements, which depositors could explain in more detail with the free text field as needed:

- a. In Copyright
- b. In Copyright - Educational Use Permitted
- c. In Copyright - EU Orphan work
- d. No Copyright

To help encourage clarity and good practice, where **No Copyright** is selected in the rights field for the digital asset, the depositor will be offered a limited subset of values in the licence field to choose from: CC0 and Public Domain Mark.

There was some concern that depositors who had previously populated the rights field with helpful free text information, such as details associated with Orphan Works, would cease to provide that additional detail if a drop-down menu was the only required rights field. It was decided to keep the mandatory free text field in addition to the Rights Statements. To disambiguate between the machine-readable Rights Statements values and the free text entry, it was proposed that a new metadata element called 'Copyright Status' should be added. It was also considered beneficial to re-label 'Licence' to 'Reuse Licence' to make clearer the different applications of the rights field versus the licence field.

Result

As part of this WorldFAIR recommendation, and in line with best practice, a CC0 public domain licence is applied to all new metadata that appears in the repository by default, with a derogation process available to CC-BY on request, provided specified criteria are met. This is separate to any licence that a depositor may set for the reuse of their digital asset/object.

Language
English

Rights
Copyright Cuimhneamh an Chláir / Clare Memories. Cuimhneamh an Chláir provides access to these transcripts / recordings on the understanding that they are for personal enjoyment. If you wish to use the material in any form of research, publication or presentation online or in person, you will need to specify that use and seek specific permission from Cuimhneamh an Chláir at info@clarememories.ie. Your request will then be reviewed by Cuimhneamh an Chláir and will be subject to a licensing agreement (at no cost).

Licence
All Rights Reserved. This object is not licenced for general reuse. Please see Rights Statement for more detail.

Depositing Organisation
Cuimhneamh an Chláir / Clare Memories

Metadata Licence
All metadata in the Repository is licensed CC0 unless otherwise indicated. For the reuse of digital assets and objects please see individual records.

Organisations and Sponsors

Cuimhneamh an Chláir
CLARE MEMORIES

Fig 6. CC0 licence statement on all landing pages (Source: DRI test environment).

A clear CC0 declaration on both object and collection landing pages will state: “All metadata in the repository is licensed CC0 unless otherwise indicated. For the reuse of digital assets and objects please see individual records” (Fig 6).

Rights Statements, Creative Commons licences and ODC licence⁷⁴ options are available from drop-down menus and as part of the batch ingest workflow. The existing Rights field is retained and remains a mandatory field for clarifying information about the Rights Statement selected. A new element, ‘Copyright Status’, is provided, to be populated from a dropdown list of values. The Licence field is renamed ‘Reuse Licence’ to encourage clearer understanding of the purpose of that element. See [Appendix II](#) for more details of implementation decisions.

DRI offers depositors and end users detailed training in the use of rights and licences within the repository. These materials are currently undergoing updates to reflect and communicate the value of these changes.

⁷⁴ <https://opendatacommons.org/>

2.5 Delivery

This recommendation was the one that DRI was most compliant with in advance of the implementation phase. As noted in D13.2 “... (re)usability of data is dependent on users being able to link to datasets and ensure the links keep working...[and]...Protocols and frameworks, when widely adopted, offer a means to provide compliance with many of the elements of the FAIR principles”.

DRI mints Digital Object Identifiers (DOI) for all of the published collections and objects in the repository. The use of Persistent Identifiers, such as DOIs, is well-established across the research sector, endorsed by organisations like the Research Data Alliance via a number of global Interest and Working Groups⁷⁵ and in emerging national PID strategies, including Ireland’s developing strategy⁷⁶. PIDs are less widely adopted in the cultural heritage sector, though the use of unique identifiers is an important part of the management of cultural heritage artefacts and records. Still, DRI’s use of the DataCite service to both mint and manage DOIs is already arguably an innovative FAIR aligning practice. As stated in DRI’s ‘Factsheet Series No 7: Persistent Identifiers and DOIs’ (2021), “The use of persistent identifiers allows researchers and scholars to cite digital objects in their work, and ensures that these citations remain correct and accessible. Persistent identifiers facilitate easy dissemination and reuse of data, allow the use and impact of data to be tracked, and create a structure that recognises and rewards data producers.”⁷⁷.

The adoption of a standardised and open exchange format such as the International Image Interoperability Framework (IIIF), identified in our previous reports as a key technology to aid in the discovery and interoperability of image files and their metadata, offers a clear pathway to support the FAIR principles⁷⁸: IIIF supports unique identifiers, provides open access to metadata via the IIIF Manifest, and operates via an agreed standard API to allow multiple tools and collections to access and use the data⁷⁹. Again, this framework and related open software environments are already in use at DRI – an OpenSeadragon viewer is deployed in the repository, with a Mirador viewer accessible through the IIIF icon.

There is perhaps the greatest opportunity to explore improved semantic interoperability by interrogating DRI’s deployment of Linked Open Data (LOD), already widely used in the cultural heritage domain^{80,81}. As noted in D13.2, “The use of LOD has the potential to both add complexity through the use of agreed-upon vocabulary terms and authority metadata, and can also be used to build relationships which put the metadata in dialogue with emerging ideas and practices. LOD

⁷⁵ https://www.rd-alliance.org/search/site/PID?f%5B0%5D=bundle%3Aworking_groups

⁷⁶ <https://norf.ie/morebrains-cooperative/>

⁷⁷ <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.bk12p0477>

⁷⁸ <https://zenodo.org/record/6779595>

⁷⁹ <https://iiif.io/>

⁸⁰ <https://dl.acm.org/doi/pdf/10.1145/3429458>

⁸¹ <https://www.kbr.be/en/projects/lod-isni/>

resources are often provided by established collecting institutions, but they may also be published by researchers, communities or smaller organisations, which should be encouraged”.

DRI supports key international vocabularies such as the Library of Congress Subject Headings⁸² and has also put resources into developing linguistically- and culturally-specific resources to improve access to Irish data: ‘Linked Logainm’ was a collaborative project led by the Digital Repository of Ireland (DRI), the Digital Enterprise Research Institute (DERI), Fiontar at Dublin City University (DCU), and the National Library of Ireland (NLI) and the Placenames Branch of the Department of Arts, Heritage and the Gaeltacht to create an LOD version of the authoritative bilingual database of Irish place names, logainm.ie⁸³.

Recommendation 5	Delivery
Details of Recommendation - as per 13.2	
Improved support for identifier schemes, APIs and machine-readable contextual data.	
FAIR alignment - as per 13.2	
FAIR recognises the value of PIDs in aiding discovery, accessibility and interoperability of data and metadata, but stable links of any kind to the semantic web of data has a potentially significant implication for reusability as well. Linked Open Data (LOD) offers connections to concepts which aid the understanding of ideas in multiple languages, and help to tell the stories of creators, owners and communities that inform those connections. Standardised frameworks enable interoperability by presenting structured machine-actionable data.	
Snapshot - DRI in relation to Recommendation 5 - Delivery	

⁸² <https://www.loc.gov/aba/publications/FreeLCSH/freelcsh.html>

⁸³ <https://repository.dri.ie/catalog/t435vt72m>

As D13.1 notes ‘The repository supports the export of data in the BagIt⁸⁴ format, and provides an OAI-PMH feed for metadata harvesting as either native Dublin Core or conforming to the Europeana Data Model. An API⁸⁵ is also available for developers wishing to interact with metadata in the repository. DOIs are issued for every collection and every object record through DataCite⁸⁶. For image files specifically, end users are able to view both IIIF manifests⁸⁷ and the underlying RDF⁸⁸ directly from the object page’.

DRI has also recently implemented FAIR signposting⁸⁹ to enhance the machine-readability of its resources, and it currently meets the requirements for Level 2 or “a comprehensive set of typed links via a link set”⁹⁰. A number of widely-recognised controlled vocabulary and authority files are in use by depositors and supported by the repository.

Analysis and recommended actions

Considering the technological supports for image discovery and delivery already in place for DRI, it was determined that any further technical enhancements should be responsive to depositor and user needs. Following the model already demonstrated in Always Already Computational: Collections as Data⁹¹, which “generated the creation of nearly a dozen deliverables meant to guide institutions as they consider development of collections as data”⁹², it was suggested that the creation of examples for depositors of well-described and constructed collection datasets that enable creative and educational reuse would offer DRI insights into the best way forward to improve current repository functionality.

The upcoming DPASSH conference (Digital Preservation in the Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences) hosted jointly by DRI, the University of Limerick and the Hunt Museum, Limerick in June 2024, will offer a collaborative opportunity to work with staff, faculty and students at the University of Limerick to help co-create these resources while also testing DRI’s metadata export functionality and IIIF deployment.

Implementation timeline

⁸⁴ <https://www.ietf.org/rfc/rfc8493.txt>

⁸⁵ <https://repository.dri.ie/api-docs/index.html>

⁸⁶ <https://datacite.org>

⁸⁷ <https://repository.dri.ie/mirador/?manifest=https://repository.dri.ie/iiif/gh93ws381/sequence.json>

⁸⁸ <https://repository.dri.ie/catalog/gh93ws381.ttl>

⁸⁹ <https://dri.ie/news/fair-signposting-helps-users-to-navigate-the-scholarly-web/>

⁹⁰ <https://signposting.org/FAIR/#level2>

⁹¹ <https://collectionsasdata.github.io>

⁹² <https://collectionsasdata.github.io/>

January 24	February 24	March 24	April 24	May 24
Review LOD		Identify Use Cases		Pilot

Discussion (process, outcomes, challenges, unexpected consequences)

In general terms, DRI was felt to comply well with this recommendation. In addition to existing functionality, the proposed implementation of Datasheets for Datasets in response to Recommendation 3 will enhance the machine-readability of DRI’s contextual and technical image data.

One long-outstanding issue with DRI’s IIF deployment is that we use JPG (and the Loris server, chosen as not all servers supported JPG at the time IIF was deployed in the repository) rather than a tiled format like JPEG2000 or PTIFF. This does result in poorer performance with larger images, but the solution would be to convert all the existing content to larger image formats, requiring extra storage, as those image formats can be large.

While it would be possible to provide a SPARQL endpoint as an additional delivery mechanism, this feature has not yet been requested by either members or users of the repository. This may be considered in response to the user dataset case study efforts.

It should be noted that DRI’s API is currently available only by request, rather than freely downloadable from the repository website, as there are concerns about the volume of requests it could generate. There are thousands of digital objects in the repository which each have their own landing pages. The cultural heritage sector has typically not supported bulk download of files from collections websites precisely because of the level of detail at which items are typically catalogued, and the fact that they are often presented 1-to-1.

Result

Development of further use cases for well-formed collections and datasets that encourage and enable creative and educational reuse is proposed in the coming months. A sample use case can be seen in [Appendix III](#).

In parallel to the work of the WorldFAIR project, DRI was successful in receiving funding from the FAIR-IMPACT project⁹³ to implement FAIR signposting within the repository⁹⁴. While not an output of WorldFAIR, the decision to implement FAIR signposting was a complementary activity.

⁹³ <https://fair-impact.eu/>

⁹⁴ <https://dri.ie/news/fair-signposting-helps-users-to-navigate-the-scholarly-web/>

3. Conclusion

As the final deliverable for Work Package 13 of the WorldFAIR project, this report has provided a summary of key changes to processes and workflows, current and ongoing in DRI, as required for the successful implementation of the recommendations delivered in D13.2. This report is envisaged as providing a reproducible roadmap for other organisations who wish to implement the recommendations identified in D13.2 and embed FAIR principles into their work practices.

It is important to note that many of the recommendations are still in the process of agreement and implementation in DRI, with a number of key decisions having already been taken to support a period of testing and review. In addition to this report, DRI is in the process of producing a series of related publications to showcase the results. The project team believes that these resources will provide invaluable insight to other cultural heritage organisations, by drilling down into the practical considerations that the recommendations demand.

The next step for DRI will be to engage with its members, via training and informational sessions, to communicate the benefits that will be accrued by responding to new options in the repository that will enable them to create more FAIR-compliant collections as data. While we anticipate more feedback and refinement of the actions taken in this report, we are confident that all and any changes will have a significantly positive impact on the interoperability of cultural heritage data shared in the repository.

4. Future work

While outside the scope of this deliverable, it should be noted that RO-Crate⁹⁵ has been established as a community-supported method for practically achieving FAIR packaging of research objects⁹⁶ (digital objects like data, methods, software, etc.) with their structured metadata. RO-Crate is based on well-established Web standards and FAIR principles. It is being adopted by a range of EU/EOSC projects and can be seen as a pragmatic implementation⁹⁷ of the FAIR digital objects vision as highlighted by EOSC's Interoperability Framework^{98,99}. DRI was awarded a grant to participate in the

⁹⁵ <https://w3id.org/ro/crate>

⁹⁶ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.websem.2015.01.003>

⁹⁷ <https://doi.org/10.3897/rio.8.e93937>

⁹⁸ <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/620649>

⁹⁹ <https://dri.ie/news/dri-and-fair-impact-making-research-data-more-fair/>

FAIR-IMPACT project¹⁰⁰, which gave us access to expertise and advice in utilising both FAIR Signposting, a standardised way for machine agents to navigate scholarly web objects, and RO Crate. As of this report, FAIR Signposting has been successfully deployed¹⁰¹.

¹⁰⁰ <https://dri.ie/news/dri-and-fair-impact-making-research-data-more-fair/>

¹⁰¹ <https://dri.ie/news/fair-signposting-helps-users-to-navigate-the-scholarly-web/>

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Appendix I - DRI Member Digitisation Workflows

DRI Member Digitisation Workflows

for 2D image files

The following survey is being conducted to improve the Digital Repository of Ireland's understanding of the technical processes and metadata workflows that our members use to digitise and share images in the Repository, in order to better tailor our support for this work and deliver the most complete information available to our users.

If your organisation does not currently host image collections in the Repository but you have workflows for image collections hosted on other platforms, we would still welcome your participation.

Survey Background:

DRI is making a commitment as part of the WorldFAIR Project to improve the transparency of technical information associated with digital assets accessed through the Repository. In response to Recommendation #2 in the [Cultural Heritage Image Sharing Recommendations Report](#), DRI aims to support end-user access to embedded metadata, as well as easier citation of image formats and their provenance. You can read more about the Cultural Heritage Image Sharing Case Study DRI is leading in the WorldFAIR Project on our website: <https://dri.ie/the-worldfair-project/>.

Data Collection and Privacy:

Access to the survey data collected will be restricted to DRI staff managing the study. Anonymised results from this survey may be shared in DRI webinars and publications, for the benefit of other repositories and professionals working with cultural heritage data. If you have any questions or concerns about how the data

will be managed and shared, please contact Beth Knazook, Research Data Project Manager at b.knazook@ria.ie.

Note on this version:

This version of the DRI Member Digitisation Workflows survey is provided as a google doc to facilitate the sharing of questions to external organisations and vendors to whom digitisation has been outsourced. Please complete the survey [here](#) to ensure that your organisation's responses have been captured by DRI.

About your organisation

DRI is attempting to create a snapshot of current member practices, however we welcome a wide range of responses to this survey from members and non-members alike, about embedded metadata practices and digitisation workflows for image files.

1. **Is your organisation:**
 - a. Full Member of DRI
 - b. Associate Member of DRI
 - c. Community Archive Award recipient
 - d. Not a member, but affiliated with a current member
 - e. An organisation that digitisation is outsourced to
 - f. None of the above

2. **What professional field of work would you say guides your organisational practices around digitisation and metadata creation? Select all that apply.**
 - a. Archives
 - b. Libraries (Research)
 - c. Libraries (Public)
 - d. Museums
 - e. Galleries
 - f. Higher Education
 - g. Other

Digitisation Workflows

The following questions are about the process your organisation typically undertakes for digitising physical materials (photographs, objects, books, graphic materials, artworks, etc.) to create a 2D

digital representation. If you outsource digitisation to another organisation or vendor, you may wish to share a copy of these questions to send to them.

You can skip or answer 'I don't know' for any questions you are unsure of.

3. What kind of hardware do you use to create digital images from physical materials? Select all that apply.

- a. Sheetfed document scanner (e.g. photocopier, printer, fax machine)
- b. Flatbed scanner
- c. Specialised scanner (e.g. film scanner, book scanner)
- d. Point-and-shoot camera
- e. Camera with manual adjustment (e.g. DSLR)
- f. Copy-stand (including camera, tripod, and one or two directional lights)
- g. Smartphone
- h. Other (please elaborate)

4. What kind of software do you use for image capture? Select all that apply.

- a. Professional scanner application that came with the scanner (e.g. Epson, Canon, etc.)
- b. Specialised photo editing tools (e.g. Adobe Photoshop, Windows Scan, GIMP)
- c. Smartphone application
- d. Camera software
- e. Other (please elaborate)

5. What kind of image processing is performed as part of your usual workflow? Select all that apply.

- a. Cropping
- b. Adjustment of brightness or tone
- c. Colour enhancement
- d. Digital dust removal
- e. Reduction of bit depth
- f. Other (please elaborate)
- g. None

6. How many of these different types of images are generated by your workflow? Select all that apply.

- a. Original (raw or unedited)
- b. Original (edited)
- c. Derivative (unedited, but reduced in scale or saved in a web accessible file format)
- d. Derivative (edited)
- e. Other (please elaborate)

7. Do you add or remove metadata from the image file at any stage in your workflow? Select all that apply.

NB: Metadata is typically embedded by camera and scanner software at the point of creation, which may include: the software and hardware used, date of creation, and particularly in the case of smartphone pictures, geographic location. Sometimes this metadata is removed when files are opened and saved after editing.)

- a. Camera-generated metadata is retained by all versions of the files
- b. Camera-generated metadata is stripped out or overwritten when new files are saved
- c. Descriptive metadata is added, such as name, rights and author information
- d. Technical metadata is added, such as PIDs
- e. No metadata is added
- f. No metadata is removed
- g. I don't know
- h. Other (please elaborate)

8. Do you use any specialised tools to add, check, or extract metadata from the digital images you create? Select all that apply.

- a. ExifTool
- b. MediaConch
- c. Adobe Photoshop/Lightroom
- d. DigiKam
- e. I don't know
- f. Other (please elaborate)

If you answered "I don't know" to questions 5 or 6, we ask that you consider uploading an example of an original scan (unedited) as well as a digital image that has gone through your usual editing workflow (any colour correction, re-sizing, re-naming, etc.)

NB: We are asking for images only to review the embedded metadata. We will not retain these photographs for any other purpose or share the image with anyone outside of this study.

Documentation and Guidance

This section asks about how decision-making around digitisation happens in your organisation. We recognise that many organisations may not have decision-making practices that are specific to digitisation decisions, so we invite you to consider all the spaces in which digitisation is discussed.

- 9. Do you retain documentation about the selection process for digitising? (For example, committee meetings minutes, processing spreadsheets, etc.)**
- Yes
 - No
 - It depends (please elaborate)
- 10. If you answered “yes” or “it depends” to question 9 above, is this information made accessible to users outside of your organisation?**
- Yes
 - No
 - It depends (please elaborate)
- 11. In developing your digitisation workflows, did you consult any digitisation guidance resources?**
- [Federal Agencies Digital Guidelines Initiative \(FADGI\) Technical Guidelines for Digitizing Cultural Heritage Materials](#)
 - [Association for Library Collections and Technical Services \(ALCTS\) Minimum Digitization Capture Recommendations](#)
 - [Library of Congress Image Quality Standards](#)
 - [National Archives of Australia Preservation Digitisation Standards](#)
 - [ISO/TR13028 Information and documentation - Implementation guidelines for digitization of records](#)
 - [Wellcome Trust Technical Guidelines for Digitisation Projects](#)

If you adhere to guidelines other than those mentioned above please feel free to share links and recommendations.

- 12. Who creates digital images in your organisation? Select all that apply.**
- Specially trained staff
 - Experienced students or volunteers (background in archival work, photography, etc.)
 - Students or Volunteers, with some training and oversight from staff
 - Students or Volunteers, with no particular training or support
 - Digitisation is outsourced
 - Other (please elaborate)

Preservation Workflows

The following questions ask about the files that are retained at the end of a digitisation workflow.

13. If you are a current DRI member who has deposited images in the Repository, please indicate which version of the file is preserved in the Repository.

- a. Original (raw or unedited)
- b. Original (edited)
- c. Derivative (unedited, but reduced in scale or saved in a web accessible file format)
- d. Derivative (edited)
- e. Other (please elaborate)

14. Do you retain copies of any of these filetypes locally?

- a. Yes
- b. No

The following two questions ask you to consider which key pieces of information you would consider important to preserve and share alongside a digital representation of a physical object i.e. which metadata should be preserved and shared as part of the catalogue record.

Question 15 concerns metadata relating to the ORIGINAL object.

Question 16 concerns metadata relating to the DIGITAL object.

15. What key pieces of information about the ORIGINAL object would you consider important to preserve and share alongside a digital representation of a physical object?

	No opinion	Not important	Could include	Should include	Must include
Title					
Copyright (original object)					
Licence (original object)					
Source (original object)					
Creator (original object)					
Date (original object)					
Description (original object)					

Physical description (material, technique, style)					
Keywords					
Geographic location (object origin)					
Geographic location (repository)					
Credit (Photographer, artist, author)					
Identification number (original object)					
Caption					
Series/Collection information					
Exhibition history					
External links					
Other*					

*If you selected 'other' please elaborate:

16. What key pieces of information about the DIGITAL OBJECT would you consider important to preserve and share alongside a digital representation of a physical object?

	No opinion	Not important	Could include	Should include	Must include
Title					
Rights (of digital object)					
Licence (of digital object)					
Source (of digital object)					
Creator (of digital object)					
Date of creation (of digital object)					

Date of publication (of digital object)					
Publisher (of digital object)					
Description					
Extent and format (of digital object)					
Keywords					
Geographic location (repository)					
Credit (Digitiser, Curator)					
Identification number (of digital object)					
Caption					
Series/Collection information (of digital object)					
Exhibition history (of digital object)					
External links					
Other*					

*If you selected 'other' please elaborate:

17. Are there any comments or questions about embedded image file metadata that you feel were not addressed by this survey?

OPTIONAL

To aid our analysis of this survey's results, please consider uploading an example of an original scan (unedited) as well as a digital image that has gone through your usual editing workflow (any colour correction, re-sizing, re-naming, etc.)

NB: We are asking for images only to review the embedded metadata. We will not retain these photographs for any other purpose or share the image with anyone outside of this study.

Please see [here](https://form.jotform.com/231233296124954) for file upload functionality as part of the survey response
<https://form.jotform.com/231233296124954>

Appendix II - Licensing and Rights Implementation Decisions

The following information expands upon decisions made in support of [2.4 Licensing & Rights](#).

Rights Implementation

To disambiguate between the machine readable rights statements values, and other instances of the Rights field containing free text, a new element called **Copyright Status** will be added.

The **Copyright Status** element will be populated from a subset of values provided by [Rightsstatements.org](https://rightsstatements.org) with the addition of a Creative Commons Public Domain deed for content that has no copyright.

UI - Human Readable value	Machine readable value
In Copyright	http://rightsstatements.org/vocab/InC/1.0/
In Copyright - Educational Use Permitted	http://rightsstatements.org/vocab/InC-EDU/1.0/
In Copyright - EU Orphan work	http://rightsstatements.org/vocab/InC-OW-EU/1.0/
No Copyright	https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/mark/1.0/

Table 3. Rights statements available to depositor (Sources: www.rightsstatements.org; <https://creativecommons.org>).

The existing Rights element will be retained as a mandatory element populated by free text to ensure as much provenance information as possible is provided by the depositor and made available to the user.

Discussion

Rightsstatements.org offers 12 different rights statements, but during implementation discussions this was felt to be too granular, potentially causing even greater confusion for depositors. For the purposes of DRI, in its role as a publisher of digital content, the key values needed are simply whether the item is in copyright or out of copyright. Other organisations may have different requirements and prefer to implement all variants of the Rights Statements.

Interestingly, the controlled list provided by rightsstatements.org does not include a statement that asserts an asset/object is definitively out of copyright. Rights Statements suggest using the PDM ([Public Domain Mark](#)) in such cases, a deed supplied as part of the Creative Commons licence suite.

For DRI's specific workflow and depositor-base it was felt that this attribution should be labelled 'No Copyright' in the UI and ingest form. If the depositor selects this option then the licences available to them in the Licence element will be limited to CC0 or the Public Domain Mark.

Licensing Implementation

Repository metadata

The recommendation is to clearly indicate that CC0 applies to repository metadata, unless otherwise stated by the depositor. Implementation has included updating a range of documents, guidance and tool tips. This will also help to explicitly differentiate between the licence status of metadata and the digital assets/objects.

There will be a static statement on each record such as: 'All metadata in the repository is licensed CC0 unless otherwise indicated. For the reuse of digital assets and objects please see individual records.'

DRI will facilitate requests from depositors for a derogation from the default CC0 licence to a CC-BY licence, on a case by case basis, for both legacy and new collections where a depositor believes that the metadata contains **significant original creative work** or the metadata has previously been published elsewhere with a different explicit licence that the depositor is legally bound to maintain.

When seeking a change from CC0 to CC-BY the Digital Archivist may consider:

- Quantity/quality of original content
- Benchmarking against similar collections or projects
- Whether original content was funded primarily through use of public funds

Digital assets, objects and collections

The Licence is currently set at collection level and is inherited at object level. It may be edited at either level after ingest.

Renaming of the Licence element to **Reuse Licence**, populated from standard lists provided by Creative Common and ODL, in the following order:

- a. Not licensed for reuse. See Additional Licence and Rights Information.
- b. CC-BY
- c. CC-BY-SA
- d. CC-BY-NC
- e. CC-BY-ND

- f. CC-BY-NC-SA
- g. CC-BY-NC-ND
- h. CC0
- i. ODC-ODbL
- j. ODC-BY
- k. ODC-PPDL

The depositors attention should also be drawn to the fact that the licence applies to the digital asset/object in training and guidance publications, and it should be reiterated that an asset in the public domain requires a CC0 licence (if you are the rights holder and are waiving your rights) or Public Domain Mark (if you are not the rights holder).

The value 'Not licensed for reuse. See Additional Licence and Rights Information' will remain at the top of the dropdown list. This will be the default value, should depositors fail to select a licence in error. This is considered a significant point for the implementation in order to prevent the accidental waiving of rights. CC licences, once issued, cannot be revoked.

Appendix III - Use Case: Collection as Data

As part of the implementation of [2.5 Delivery](#) the development of use cases for well-formed collections and datasets that enable creative and educational reuse is proposed in the coming months. A sample use case developed by DRI staff for instructional purposes is provided below.

Use Case: **Analysis of themes within a Collection**
Source: Cuimhneamh an Chláir / Clare Memories Oral History Collection
Location: DOI: [10.7486/DRI.td96zw92b](https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.td96zw92b)
Method used: pyLDA
Field selected: Description
Purpose: To utilise machine learning to detect word and phrase patterns within DRI object record metadata describing audio files and textual transcriptions of oral history interviews, and present the relationships between the most common terms visually.

Using the functionality to export the metadata associated with all objects in a collection or sub-collection as a CSV file on the Collection landing page a CSV file is generated. This dataset can then be analysed using a wide range of tools, in this case we have selected Topic Modelling functionality in Coconut Libtool¹⁰².

Fig 7. Forthcoming functionality to allow export of all object metadata within a collection on collection landing page.

¹⁰² <https://www.coconut-libtool.com/home>

View Collection

An export of this collection is being created. You will receive an email when it is available.

Export all Metadata

Choose fields to export for each object in the collection. The metadata will be exported as a CSV file for you to download.

- Toggle all
- Title
- Creator
- Contributor
- Publisher
- Description
- Creation date
- Published date
- Date
- Identifiers
- Subjects
- Subjects (temporal)
- Subjects (places)
- Relations
- Rights
- Status
- Assets

Submit

Fig 8. Options to select data elements from objects in a collection for export to CSV.

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O
Id	Title	Creator	Descriptio	Descriptio	Creation [Date	Identifiers	Subjects	Subjects_	Subjects_	Subjects_	Subjects_	Subjects_	Subjects_ (Su
22281j09g	Nan Aherr	Cuimhne	This is an		name=192	name=201	CanC_OH	Ireland--S	http://id.l	Country li	http://id.l	Folklore--	http://id.l	McNamar ht
3b59f401w	Peggy Hog	Cuimhne	This is an		name=193	name=201	CanC_OH	Ireland--S	http://id.l	Ireland--R	http://id.l	Folklore--	http://id.l	Folk song; ht
4b29r141f	Peggy Hog	Cuimhne	This is an		name=192	name=201	CanC_OH	Ireland--S	http://id.l	Ireland--R	http://id.l	Women--l	http://id.l	Folklore-- ht
8c980j85p	Nora McM	Cuimhne	This is an		name=201	CanC_OH	Ireland--S	http://id.l	Ireland--R	http://id.l	Women--l	http://id.l	World Wa	ht
8g851f69j	Clare Ora	Cuimhne	This is the	audio file for an epis	name=202	CanC_OH	Ireland--S	http://id.l	Ireland--R	http://id.l	Women--l	http://id.loc.gov/autho		
tm711p60j	Meaney si	Cuimhne	This is a		name=193	name=201	CanC_OH	Ireland--S	http://id.l	Ireland--R	http://id.l	Folklore--	http://id.l	Folk musi ht
tq582k44t	Moirá Gar	Cuimhne	This is an		name=193	name=201	CanC_OH	Ireland--S	http://id.l	Ireland--R	http://id.l	Women--l	http://id.l	Folklore-- ht
tt453g28p	Annie Cor	Cuimhne	This is an		name=193	name=201	CanC_OH	Ireland--S	http://id.l	Ireland--R	http://id.l	Saint Step	http://id.l	Education; ht
0 tx324c121	Maura Mc	Cuimhne	This is a		name=192	name=200	CanC_OH	Ireland--S	http://id.l	Ireland--R	http://id.l	Blacksmit	http://id.loc.gov/autho	
1 v4066480r	Nora Can	Cuimhne	This is an		name=191	name=201	CanC_OH	Ireland--S	http://id.l	Country li	http://id.l	Women--l	http://id.l	Folk musi ht
2 xw432332s	Susan Bar	Cuimhne	This is an		name=193	name=201	CanC_OH	Ireland--S	http://id.l	Ireland--R	http://id.l	Women--l	http://id.l	Folk danc ht
3 z8915n681	Susan Wil	Cuimhne	This is an	Worked	name=192	name=201	CanC_OH	Ireland--S	http://id.l	Ireland--R	http://id.l	Women--l	http://id.l	Folklore-- ht

Fig 9. Screenshot of use case data export as CSV.

Fig 10. Topic modelling based on the use case dataset (in Coconut Libtool).